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COMPONENTS OF PEDAGOGICAL SKILL AND THEIR ESSENCE

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***Annotation.** In modern literature in the field of pedagogy and psychology, we come across different explanations of the concept of "Pedagogical skill".*

It can be said that the essence of this concept is given in "Pedagogical encyclopedia". In our opinion, compared to others, this definition somewhat correctly illuminates the content and essence of pedagogical skill: It is an art that provides the opportunity to reach a high level in education and training and to constantly improve it, and love the child. It is the work of every pedagogue who loves his profession.

***Keyword:** teacher, pedagogue, mastered, cultural, personal, wealth, individual*

***Аннотация.** В современной литературе в области педагогики и психологии мы встречаем разные объяснения понятия «Педагогическое мастерство».*

Можно сказать, что суть этого понятия изложена в «Педагогической энциклопедии». На наш взгляд, по сравнению с другими, это определение несколько правильно освещает содержание и сущность педагогического мастерства: Это искусство, дающее возможность достичь высокого уровня в воспитании и обучении, постоянно совершенствовать его, любить ребенка. Это работа каждого педагога, любящего свою профессию.

***Ключевые слова:** учитель, педагог, освоенный, культурный, личный, богатство, индивидуальный.*

What should young teachers be like, working in the democratic and legal state that we are building in independent Uzbekistan at the present time? The most important basis for the personality of a modern educator is the discipline. An educator is a person with a very high level of general culture. He needs to know a lot, to be aware of the advances in the field of science that he is studying nowadays, to be aware of the news, to teach his students to acquire knowledge every day. , he should fill and deepen his knowledge.

Trainers and educators working in MTM should also have the following psychophysiological features:

- good health,
- common sense,
- physical well-being,
- endurance,
- diligence,
- enthusiasm, eagerness to be,

In addition, the following qualities should be present in order for educators to be skilled

- Constructive, (fair organization of work processes for the development of constructive thinking)
- Analytical, (required to monitor and analyze the child's work and drawings through analytical thinking)
- Creative (Creative thinking is the independent solution of any assignment or task in the process of professional activity.) they should also be able to think independently.

In addition, the speech culture of coaches and educators is also important in this process. For this, they should also be demanding of their speech culture. The demand for them can be expressed as follows. Pedagogical behavior is a manifestation of the teacher's professional activity and reflects the interaction and cooperation of the participants of this process in education.

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